

Stuttering, Self-Esteem and School Performance for Successful Professional Integration at “Lycee Hotelier D'abidjan-Cocody”

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Abstract :- Stuttering is defined as a language difficulty or disorder that subjects the speaking subject to stress and a physiological imbalance in a communication situation. In the context of school learning and more specifically professional training, stuttering learners are generally marginalized and underestimated. Such a discriminatory observation in educational institutions, at a time when we are talking more and more about inclusive schools, leads us to conduct a study at the hotel school of Abidjan Cocody. The main objective of the study is to analyze the self-esteem of stutterers in relation to their school results and their professional integration. Based on the hypothesis that a strong self-esteem pushes the student who stutters to develop skills and have better academic performance, the study is subject to an experimental approach supported by the quantitative method. With a sample of 28 student trainees at the end of their training, made up of 12 girls and 16 boys, Coopersmith's SEI technique and data collection instruments such as the interview, the observation questionnaire and the focus group, are summoned in this work to perceive the correlation between the variables present. The statistical analysis of the data, with the use of the SPSS software, proceeds to the calculations of the chi-squares and provides results according to which the high self-esteem remains the only alternative for the stuttering trainee to develop school performance and thus facilitate, his professional integration.

Keywords:- Stuttering; Self-esteem; Sex; School performance; occupational integration.

I. INTRODUCTION

Among the language difficulties and disorders identified in schools in Côte d'Ivoire, stuttering stands out as one of the most common. From primary to secondary school, many students are confronted with this language pathology which, from the point of view of certain previous scientific works (2008)¹, affects the rhythm and rate of speech. Thus, according to these same scientific sources, stuttering is defined by the involuntary repetition or prolongation of sounds, syllables or words disturbing verbal fluency in the absence of organic abnormality. The frequency of words and sentences experiences a disconcerting irregularity and the speaker's speech is discontinuous. Stuttering can appear in children in an

insidious way or suddenly; in the latter case, it occurs as a result of an emotional shock. It is around six years old, the age of entry into primary school, that the manifestations of this disorder are pronounced in children and impact both their socialization and the nature of the interactions they develop with their immediate environment.

Set back or marginalized in one way or another at school, stutterers show exceptional cognitive potential in all areas of life, particularly in the school setting where the work of Séka (2017) shows us shed light on the first ranks they occupy in the learning of disciplines such as mathematics. The lack of fluent speech among stutterers pushes them rather towards the assiduous learning of disciplines that make less use of spoken language. Our society itself shows us daily that around us, the stutterers who succeed in their studies, are in scientific fields, where speech is less solicited. This observation, far from being ruled out, allows us to put this point of view into perspective and to reconsider the developmental potential of these stuttering individuals in many other fields such as the hotel industry where communication is a fundamental given. Our field of study is the hotel school of Abidjan Cocody where the type of education provided is formative and professional; the teaching of classical disciplines in their majority is excluded.

The study to be conducted relates to stuttering, self-esteem and school performance for successful professional integration among trainee students of the said high school. The social interest of this study lies in a school context where, far from being traditional, the teaching is fundamentally oriented towards vocational training. Here, boys and girls constitute the population of learners and the disciplines taught are, for example, reception, culinary activities, pastry, lingerie, hygiene, accounting. It should be noted that beyond the non-exhaustive quoted subjects, communication remains essential and transversal to the different training courses. The transversal nature of the communication discipline makes it a subject with a high coefficient and conditional on academic success. It is in such a context that stutterers manage to surpass themselves by often exceeding, in the end-of-training results, many non-stuttering learners who nevertheless had the advantage of linguistic fluency. It is safe to point out that awareness of the verbal deficit gives rise to a high level of self-esteem in stutterers, capable of drowning out the disability and therefore preparing them to focus on their socio-professional integration. In the series of scientific works that have focused on the relationship of self-esteem and performanceschools,

¹Psy : le langage. Repéré dans <http://berrehal.unblog.fr>

the unanimity around the significance between the two variables suffers from no dispute (Bloom, 1979; Gerardi, 1990). In the same vein, similar studies are carried out on the influence of parental educational practices, self-esteem and academic success in students who evolve in a climate of school adaptation.

Based on Lautrey's theory of family educational practices (1980) and Coopersmith's Self-Esteem Inventory (1967), the results of these studies conducted by Allès-Jardel, Metral and Scopellitti (2000) show the existence of a significant link of parental educational practices on self-esteem which inevitably induces the influence of the level of self-esteem on school performance.

Caille & O' Prey (2006) tend to focus their work on terminal students, in a situation of physical development and cognitive reasoning. They find that the differences in school performance observed among these students are far from being dependent on the level of self-esteem they develop physically and socially. However, according to Caille and O'prey, the observation of a strong correlation may be relevant when the student communicates frequently with his parents regardless of the social environment to which he belongs. The effect of family structuring, as argued by Lautrey (1980), then takes on its full meaning in academic success among mature adolescents.

For his part, Bawa (2007) conducted a study among Togolese adolescents aged between 14 and 16 years. The study aims to analyze the effect of the influence of self-esteem on school performance with a sample of 48 students belonging variously to all social strata. Still using Coopersmith's IES (Self-Esteem Inventory) methods, cross-referenced with the feelings developed by the students, the author reveals that his results indicate a significant relationship between self-esteem and school performance. His starting hypothesis which states that adolescents with positive self-esteem have a high success rate compared to adolescents with negative self-esteem is thus verified.

To understand the effect of self-esteem in stutterers on the academic performance they develop and on their socio-professional integration, it is useful to consider, in the present study, Lawrence's theoretical model of self-concept (1988) and Harter (1998). These two authors support the idea that the variation of self-esteem depends on the importance that the individual gives to an area of his life, and the role played by other significant people around him.

The interpretation of the self-concept schema² of Harter and Lawrence, brings together in an individual, two distinct variables which are the self-image, expressing his real or current identity and the ideal self-translating the desired identity. The gap observed by the individual, between his present self and his envisioned self, arouses in him a self-assessment which will cause the emergence of a

self-esteem whose level of appreciation will impact his academic and social skills.

Transposed to the field of school learning, Duclos³ (2010: 4) shows, from a pedagogical angle, how self-esteem can be a source of motivation for students. To this end, he argues that *a child cannot hope to achieve a goal or achieve success if he is not aware of his personal value. In other words, the child, in order to know success, must rely on the memory of its past successes; this is the condition for him to be able to realistically anticipate the possibility of experiencing another success. But the memory of his successes only comes to him if the adult has pointed them out to him as they go along; the adult must also have taken care to frequently reactivate this memory while proposing new challenges or new lessons. The child draws from this memory the energy and the hope necessary to persevere in his efforts. By experiencing success, he acquires a personal pride that fuels his self-esteem. It is the dynamic cycle of learning in which self-esteem is the essential foundation.*

The studies carried out on self-esteem in relation to school performance are undeniably numerous. Their multitude, on the contrary, situates us on the importance and topicality of this subject in the scientific community. However, it is clear that very little literature addresses issues relating to language difficulties and disorders related to school performance among students. Also, we found an interest in exploring this scientific field which brings together stuttering, self-esteem and school results among students of the hotel school of Abidjan Cocody. Thus, the relational game that takes place between the "stuttering" and "self-esteem" variables in pupils (girls / boys) defines the level of competence of each stutterer in their school career where, it must be emphasized, communication remains a fundamental discipline.

The definitional approach to stuttering in Andrews (1964) is perceived as a speech disorder characterized by pronunciation defects. Stuttering is incorrect, disordered speech with word distortions and false connections. It is also a clumsy language where thought is expressed without order or agreement. There is therefore disorganization of verbal thought. The stutterer has difficulty organizing his sentences. Stuttering is a disorder that occurs in early childhood between the ages of 3 and 4, not when the first words appear but when the first sentences are formed, that is to say when language is organized and are the contacts with others.

For other children, the onset of stuttering is between the ages of 5 and 6 when entering primary school. Finally, stuttering can appear much later between the ages of 10 and 12; it is the moment when the subject becomes more aware of his difficulties because of the problems he is going through during this period and which can intensify and inhibit him. According to LE Huche (2005), stuttering is explained by a problem of communication with others. It is

²Source : Educa Santé (2021). Estime de soi estime des autres : Apports contemporains, repéré dans <http://www.estimesoietdesautres.be> le 31/05/2022 à 7h10.

³Mentioned by Université de Paix the 06 of January 2011 in ressourcespedagogiques

also explained by the difficulties of communication with the members of the family, it is essentially a problem of relationship, communication, psychological relationship with its environment. For Estienne (1996:181), stuttering can be described as *“a dislocation of the rhythm and flow of speech, generated by an overtension of the phonatory organs resulting in an accumulation of articulatory and vocal hitches of various and unpredictable types. These snags disarticulate the temporal organization of discourse in an anarchic way, to the point of parasitizing the alternations of silences and sounds around which meaning is organized.”*

Stuttering takes two different forms. The clonic form whose major characteristic is the repetition of syllables or a group of syllables. The tonic form which presents a spasmodic aspect of speech with more or less significant blockages either at the beginning or during the sentence. Tonic stuttering can also take the inspiratory form. In very serious cases, it is manifested by a tension of the whole body by a fixity of the gaze in particular which are marks of a very great inner disarray. Since stuttering is usually related to exhalation, the subject stutters mainly when he is tired or irritated. For most stutterers, the embarrassment is at the time of the elaboration of thought into language. The enumeration of all these characteristics indicates in a significant way that stuttering is an important language disorder which is difficult to manage for the child who is entering his adolescent phase. It is also rightly that Van Hout (2002), admits in his research that stuttering is part of language disorders, the one that offers so many mysteries and controversies. Indeed, deprived of the oratorical contest, the stutterer manages to develop performances not only in written language but also in other disciplinary fields which earn him admiration and respect.

While the question of gender, in connection with school performance, has been addressed by authors such as Mosconi (2001), Bellat (2004), Baudelot (2013) about the subjects taught, particularly in the fields of mathematics and exact sciences, that of language development and more particularly oral communication has been the subject of scientific work with authors such as Bouchard (2008), Ginger (2015) Caris (2015) who support them, the language predominance observed in women, predominance due to the potential specificity of their brain.

In the school environment, the exact and applied sciences and the literary sciences very often share the preferences of the actors who are the pupils. Which boys or girls develop more competence in science or literature?

Boys are generally perceived as the best students in the exact and applied sciences while girls are considered as those who excel in literature, specifically in communication. This observation tends to translate a certain inequality between the two sexes, which seems to go in the direction of the work of Bellat (2004) who maintains that the school system contributes to produce inequalities and legitimize the differences between boys and girls. These inequalities, continues the author, grow as schooling progresses and promote the integration of gender stereotypes among

students; stereotypes that give the feeling that a girl or a boy has to build his personal identity by taking a position in relation to his social and professional expectations. These stereotypes, whose devaluing effect very often affects individuals, can insidiously lead to a state of failure. But how can it be that a student, consciously or unconsciously, manages to devalue himself to the point of producing counter-performances, ending in failures?

For Humbert (1992), if failure can be the consequence of a poor self-esteem, it can be assumed in return that a learner at the start, having low self-esteem, finds himself at a disadvantage in his school learning with less chance for professional integration. Self-esteem has been the subject of several studies in relation to school performance.

As underlined above, several studies have focused on the academic performance of students in relation to variables such as family practices, socio-professional categories of parents, basic applied sciences and literary sciences. The diversity of these works, as dense from the point of view of their quality, nevertheless reveals a weak prospection in the study of the combination of variables such as stuttering, self-esteem, school performance and professional integration. This study, which focused on the relationship between the self-esteem of stutterers (girls and boys) and their school results in a dynamic of professional integration, shows two indicators: the first sheds light on the level of self-esteem in stutterers determines the quality of their school results and consequently facilitates their professional integration. The second is the differential percentage between all stutterers (girls and boys) in a vocational high school where communication is undoubtedly a fundamental discipline for academic success. Which girls or boys display more self-esteem in the face of stuttering? in a school where vocational training is a priori intended for girls. The school inclusion policy gives everyone an opportunity to learn and receive training according to their defined skills and professional choices. In this sense, the sharing of vocational training modules at the Cocody hotel school between girls and boys is perfectly understandable. The event which, however, seems to us worthy of curiosity and which gives rise to the present study, is identified around observations:

Many student trainees who stutter in this school, curiously surprise all the supervisory staff by the quality of their work and the opportunity of the internships that they get with ease. The girls who, a priori, are supposed to excel in hotel training, seem to be supplanted by the boys, both in school results and professional internships.

These two observations lead us to ask ourselves the following question: How do stutterers (girls & boys) manage to overcome their handicap to be among the best learners in vocational high school and guarantee successful professional integration?

This main question aims more specifically at the formulation of subsidiary questions described as follows:

Is stuttering an asset to the development of skills in students?

What is the attitude of stutterers in hotel training towards non-stutterers?

Faced with their disability, how do stutterers feel permanently in front of others?

Is self-esteem more developed in boys than in girls?

What promotes the development of self-esteem in stutterers?

These different questions lead us to formulate the following general objective: the present study aims to analyze self-esteem among stutterers, in relation to school results and successful professional integration.

More specifically, the objective is to firstly describe the level of performance of stutterers from the hotel school of Abidjan cocody and secondly, to measure the relationship between self-esteem and academic performance of stutterers.

The study postulates the hypothesis that self-esteem is a determining factor in academic success. More specifically, we can argue that:

- The improvement in the communication of stutterers, the recorded school performance followed by socio-professional integration, are made possible by the level of self-esteem maintained.
- Gender determines the level of self-esteem among students and thus promotes improved school results and successful professional integration.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Population and sample

The study focuses on the relationship between the level of self-esteem and the academic performance of stutterers from the Lycée Professionnel Hôtelier de Cocody. The sample is made up of both girls and boys and is estimated at a population of 1,440 students. The composition of the sample is based on the reasoned choice technique. 50 subjects are selected on the basis of the indications given by the educators; these are generally students with various language disorders. Among them, 28 subjects are identified as stutterers after interview. There are 12 girls and 16 boys. The active sample is therefore composed of 28 student trainees.

B. Data collection procedure

The collection of information was based on two principles, the first of which is based on Coopersmith's self-esteem inventory. Following the test and the interview, two groups of students emerge; one exhibiting high self-esteem and the other low self-esteem. The second principle refers to students' end-of-year results.

III. DATA ANALYSIS AND PROCESSING METHODS

• Data processing is based on qualitative and quantitative analyses.

➤ Qualitative analysis

The interview was the subject of individual exchanges between the subjects and the interviewer. Given that the testimonies collected under the report of a semi-structured interview often lend themselves to quantitative analysis (digitization of the questionnaire and production of statistical data) thus facilitating the illustration of the results by figures, diagrams or histograms, the content analysis is appropriate and consistent in interpreting the results.

➤ Quantitative analysis

Since the present study connects two groups of students, the current research paradigm is one of prediction; we are looking here to understand the expected relationship between two events. Therefore, the formulation of hypotheses is necessary and the use of parametric calculations is justified. Thus, the only summoning of the qualitative analysis cannot be enough to lead the discussion and the interpretation of the results of this work. Quantitative analysis is therefore intended to be the ideal approach in the presentation of results insofar as these results are accompanied by numerical data with degrees of freedom (DOF) and contingency coefficients to be shown.

➤ Data processing instrument

The SPSS software is the instrument for processing the data collected. These are parametric calculations that will generate results after coding the data, coding made from the questionnaire submitted to the student trainees and the answers collected. The use of the Spss software is justified here, by the methodological approach taken in this study. Indeed, the quantitative approach seemed appropriate to us insofar as it allowed us to read the possible relationships between the variables of the study in play.

IV. RESULTS

A. GENDER OF SURVEYS

The sex of the respondents is specified in the table below.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	15	53,6	53,6	53,6
	Female	13	46,4	46,4	100,0
	Total	28	100,0	100,0	

Table 1

Male individuals represent the majority of respondents, ie 53.6%, while female individuals constitute 46.4% of the surveyed population.

B. STUTTERING STATUS

		Stutteringstatus			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	MildForm	12	42,9	42,9	42,9
	SevereForm	16	57,1	57,1	100,0
	Total	28	100,0	100,0	

Table 2

This study is based on a sample composed mainly of subjects with severe forms of stuttering (57.14%). Subjects with mild forms of stuttering represent 42.86% of the surveyed population.

C. STUTTERING AND SELF-ESTEEM

In order to test the relationship between self-esteem and the form of stuttering presented by the individual, the following test was carried out.

StutteringForm		General self-esteem	Social self-esteem	School self-esteem
SevereForm	Moderate	37,8333	11,7500	10,7500
	N	16	16	16
	Standard deviation	3,61395	1,81534	,75378
MildForm	Moderate	41,1250	13,8125	13,0000
	N	12	12	12
	Standard deviation	2,15639	1,47054	1,78885
Total	Moderate	39,7143	12,9286	12,0357
	N	28	28	28
	Standard deviation	3,26437	1,90377	1,81521

Table 3

The results obtained indicate that on all three dimensions of self-esteem (general, social, academic), subjects with severe forms of stuttering obtain significantly lower scores than subjects with mild forms of stuttering.

In order to statistically verify the differences in averages observed between the two groups of individuals, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney test is used, due to non-compliance with the validity conditions of the Student's T test. (normality of the distribution and homoscedasticity).

Summary of the hypothesis test

	NullHypothesis Test	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of ES_GEN_PERS is the same across the Stuttering Status categories.	Mann-Whitney U-test for independent samples	,020 ^a	Reject null hypotheses.
2	The distribution of ES_SOCIAL is the same across the Stuttering Status categories.	Mann-Whitney U-test for independent samples	,004 ^a	Rejectnullhypotheses.
3	The distribution of ES_SCOLAIRE is the same across the categories of stuttering status.	Mann-Whitney U-test for independent samples	,001 ^a	Reject null hypotheses.

Table 4

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .050.

a. The exact meaning is displayed for this test.

Performing the Mann-Whitney U test makes it possible to reject all the null hypotheses on the three (03) dimensions of the self-esteem of the subjects surveyed (P-sig <0.05). In other words, subjects with mild forms of stuttering have higher self-esteem than subjects with severe forms.

D. STUTTERING, COMMUNICATION AND SCHOOL PERFORMANCE

Crosstab Participation *Performance *Stuttering Status

Stutteringstatus	Participation	Weak communication	Performance		Total
			High Performance	Low Performance	
MildForm	Participation	Weak communication	4	3	7
		High communication	33,3%	25,0%	58,3%
	Total	High communication	5	0	5
		Weak communication	41,7%	0,0%	41,7%
SevereForm	Participation	Weak communication	1	6	7
		High communication	6,3%	37,5%	43,8%
	Total	High communication	6	3	9
		Weak communication	37,5%	18,8%	56,3%
Total	Participation	Weak communication	5	9	14
		High communication	17,9%	32,1%	50,0%
	Total	High communication	11	3	14
		Weak communication	39,3%	10,7%	50,0%
Total			16	12	28
			57,1%	42,9%	100,0%

Table 5

Of all 12 subjects with a mild form of stuttering, 41.7% of them were found to be high performers when communicating regularly. In contrast, a quarter of subjects (25%) with a mild form of stuttering produce low performance when communicating weakly.

Among all the subjects with severe forms of stuttering (N=16), more than a third of the subjects (37.5%) who communicate weakly produce consequently a low

performance. Similarly, more than a third of the subjects (37.5%) communicating regularly consequently produce a high performance.

In short, a link can be postulated between the performance of the subject and his frequency of communication. This link is subject to verification using the chi-square statistical test of independence for a significance level of 95%.

Stutteringstatus		Value	ddl	Asymptoticsignificance (two-sided)	sig. exact (two-sided)	sig. exact (one-sided)
MildForm	Pearson chi-square	2,857 ^c	1	,091		
	Correction for continuity ^b	1,029	1	,310		
	likelihood ratio	3,935	1	,047		
	Fisher's exact test				,205	,159
	Association linear by linear	2,619	1	,106		
	N# of valid observations	12				
SevereForm	khi-carré de Pearson	4,390 ^d	1	,036		
	Correction for continuity ^b	2,520	1	,112		
	likelihood ratio	4,731	1	,030		
	Fisher's exact test				,060	,055

	Association linear by linear	4,116	1		,042		
	N# of valid observations	16					
Total	Pearson chi-square	5,250 ^a	1		,022		
	Correction for continuity ^b	3,646	1		,056		
	likelihood ratio	5,445	1		,020		
	Fisher's exact test					,054	,027
	Association linear by linear	5,062	1		,024		
	N # of valid observations	28					

Table 6

a.0 cells (0.0%) have a theoretical count less than 5. The minimum theoretical count is 6.00.

b. Calculated only for a 2x2 table

vs. 3 cells (75.0%) have a theoretical number less than 5. The minimum theoretical number is 1.25.

d. 3 cells (75.0%) have a theoretical number less than 5. The minimum theoretical number is 3.06.

Symmetric measurements

Stuttering status			Value	Approximate meaning
MildForm	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	-,488	,091
		V de Cramer	,488	,091
	N of valid observations			12
SevereForm	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	-,524	,036
		V de Cramer	,524	,036
	N d'observations valides			16
Total	Nominal by Nominal	Phi	-,433	,022
		V de Cramer	,433	,022
	N of valid observations			28

Table7

The results indicate that the Chi-square test is not valid because more than 25% of the cells have a theoretical number less than 5. In this sense, the likelihood ratio test is used, which indicates p-values (p=0.030 for severe forms / p=0.047 for mild forms / p=0.020 generally) less than 0.05. The likelihood ratio test therefore confirms the significance of the relationship and makes it possible to affirm at the risk threshold $\alpha= 5\%$ that communication is a discriminating factor which intervenes significantly in the pupil's performance according to the form of stuttering that he introduces. Note that the relationship between these variables is moderate, since the values of Cramer's V oscillate between 0.433 and 0.524.

V. DISCUSSION

In view of the results presented, the hypothesis1 that stuttering students with high self-esteem perform better than those with low self-esteem is verified. In addition, their professional integration is done more quickly than the others. How did we come to this?

The superior performance of stutterers and their rapid professional integration can be understood by their ability to overcome their handicap through rehabilitation and the quality of relational contacts with their immediate surroundings. In school learning, success always starts from a good social climate and excellent relational quality with those with whom the interactional circle is maintained. Developing such an attitude presupposes an above-average

level of self-esteem. Unanimity around the value of self-esteem, which is a function of the socializing quality of the individual, is beyond doubt. It is moreover in this same ideological conception that Duclos (2010) can say that self-esteem is subordinated to the quality of the relationships that a child weaves with the people who are important to him and who are said to be "significant". Thus, the favorable remarks made by a significant adult greatly contribute to the existence of good self-esteem in a child. Conversely, negative comments or judgments can destroy the image of this child has of himself.

The quality of the inter-psyche interactions which engage the student trainees and their teachers without omitting the supervisory staff, constitutes a solid factor in the development of language, human and academic skills. The school social climate inspires a conviviality of the school actors in such a way that this creates, through this social value, a motivational dynamic that benefits stutterers. Indeed, stutterers who open up to other people without inferiority complex, consolidate themselves in their situation which, for them, is not static. The idea that they have of the presence of apparently invisible problems in non-stutterers ends up convincing them that it is social contradictions that feed and give meaning to human life.

The performance maintained by stutterers is also the result of a particular interest in the disciplines taught, which themselves have a link with the professional project of these learners. When the object of teaching produces in the learner, an interest that can satisfy his professional project, the feeling of success, which he finds within reach, brings out a motivational impulse, which is part of a valuation of the individual learner. Thus, once motivated, any element likely to trigger a complex of inability to be the best of his promotion, disappears. The stutterer surpasses himself by putting himself in a posture of self-confidence, self-affirmation combining motivation and success without any frustration even when the result obtained is not the one hoped for. This dimension of the stutterer's perception, supports (Bawa, 2002) is a guarantee of his commitment and a consequence of his convincing results. Therefore, the affective and emotional tone of self-esteem constitutes the central column of identity architecture in any individual.

The hypothesis2 according to which gender determines the level of self-esteem and promotes a better development of school results in students, is not verified. The non-confirmation of the hypothesis is explained by the psychological differences observed between men and women, the predominant factors of which are heredity and environment. While heredity gives a large place to genotypes, the environment is interested in phenotypes with a pronounced emphasis on educational and cultural influences. Also, we can see in the results that the expectations in terms of skills are more inclined in favor of the female gender because of the characteristics and norms corresponding to their status. Indeed, the school trains students in hotel trades with all recognized specialties such as catering, bedding, pastry, reception, communication and many other disciplines. These different areas of competence take on a character of sociability, a virtue that consecrates

the sensitivity of the girls. They are generally looking for harmonious relationships, promptness in household chores and are specifically attracted to communication and verbal expression. But despite the natural predispositions that make girl students the most privileged, the trend in school performance is not necessarily in their favor insofar as boys record a rate of 57.1% against 42.9%.

The numerical inferiority of girls and the overall formation of the school which affects more the educational culture of African girls, do not however guarantee for them, the primacy in the school results. School attendance and results for boys therefore indicate that the "gender" variable is far from being a performance indicator in a vocational training environment where girls are expected to develop more skills due to the nature of the training. This situation is well understood when the majority of student's mention, to justify it, self-esteem as the fundamental factor of success.

VI. CONCLUSION

The subject studied analyzes the link between stuttering, self-esteem, academic performance and professional integration among trainee students of the hotel school of Cocody. Clearly, the study highlights stuttering among student trainees and observes how self-esteem influences their results to facilitate their socio-professional integration. The general objective of this study is to analyze the variance of school results among stutterers, according to the level of self-esteem they develop. While the general hypothesis supports the idea that self-esteem is a determining factor of academic success, the operational hypotheses have made it possible to understand that improving the communication of stutterers, the academic performance they achieve, followed by socio-professional integration, are made possible by the level of self-esteem maintained. Supported by the reference theories of Harter and Lawrence (1982, 1988), verification of the first hypothesis is confirmed.

The analysis of the results obtained confirms the hypothesis that high self-esteem causes better communication in stutterers, which affects social relations and leads to better school results. Socio-professional integration is then facilitated for these stuttering subjects. However, it should be noted that the level of self-esteem is developed in stutterers according to the personality of each. The differences in performance between them are then better perceived and better understood. Stuttering does not de facto arouse self-esteem, but the development of self-esteem depends on both endogenous and heterogeneous factors in individuals.

This study undoubtedly records weaknesses that can be justified, among other things, in the composition of the sample. The results were able to show the invalid nature of the second hypothesis supporting that gender determines the level of self-esteem in students and thus promotes an improvement in school results and successful professional integration. We have found, in fact, that girls are numerically inferior to boys; parity would certainly have changed the results in favor of girls. Ultimately, in the

assertion that the hypotheses are not all verified, it is permissible to argue that the results are largely influenced by the self-esteem of the learners. Stutterers are called upon to value themselves, overcome prejudices and give a positive image of their identity despite the lack of communication fluidity. It is clear that the realization of the positive image of the stutterer can only be actualized with the accompaniment of the teachers, but especially of the parents who are called upon to provide their children with a reassuring family attachment in which the young person can to offer the luxury of imagining and realizing one's professional project

REFERENCES

- [1.] ALLES-JARDEL, M., METRAL, V. ET SCOPELLITTI, S. (2000). Pratiques éducatives parentales, estime de soi et réussite scolaire d'élèves de sixième. *La revue internationale de l'éducation familiale*, 4 (1), 63 - 91.
- [2.] ANDREWS, G. (1964). *The syndrom of stuttering*. Lavenham, British : Press, Suffolk
- [3.] BARIAUD, F. (2006). Le Self-Perception profile for Adolescents (SPPA) de S. Harter. L'orientation scolaire et professionnelle, 35 (2), 282-295.
- [4.] BOUCHARD, C. (2008). *Développement du langage des filles et des garçons franco-québécois âgés entre 8 et 30 mois*. Extrait des actes du congrès de l'Acfas de Mai 2008 au Canada.
- [5.] BAWA, I. H. (2008). *Pratiques éducatives familiales, estime de soi et performances scolaires chez des adolescents : cas des adolescents de la commune d'Atakpamé (Togo)*. Mémoire de DEA de Psychologie, Université de Lomé.
- [6.] BLOCH, H., CHEMAMA, R. ET DÉPRET, E. (1996). *Grand dictionnaire de la psychologie*. Paris : Larousse.
- [7.] BLOOM, B.S. (1979). *Caractéristiques individuelles et apprentissages scolaires*. Paris: Fernand Nathan.
- [8.] BOURCET, C. (1998). Self-evaluation and school adaptation in adolescence. *European journal of psychology of education*, 13 (4), 515-527.
- [9.] CAGLAR, H. (1989). *La psychologie scolaire*. Paris : PUF.
- [10.] CALIXTE, J. (2008). *Milieu familial et réussite scolaire*. Mémoire de licence en psychologie. Université d'Etat d'Haïti.
- [11.] CAILLE, J-P., & O'PREY, S. (2006). *Estime de soi et réussite scolaire sept ans après l'entrée en sixième*. La Revue Education et Formations, 72, 20-25
- [12.] CARIS, Ariane (2015). Pour quoi les femmes parlent - elles plus que les hommes ? Consulté dans www.conseilfeminin.com, Ouvert le 03 Avril 2022 à 10h.
- [13.] COOPERSMITH, S. (1967). *The antecedents of self-esteem*. San Francisco, CA, Freeman.
- [14.] Djè Bi, T. G. (2002). *Niveau d'aspiration et performances scolaires chez des adolescents selon la catégorie socioprofessionnelle des parents*. Thèse de doctorat de 3^{ème} cycle. Département de psychologie. Université de Cocody, Abidjan.
- [15.] Djè Bi, T. G. (2007). Pratiques éducatives chez les parents d'élèves des établissements secondaires. *Revue du CAMES*, 9, 213-221.
- [16.] DUCLOS, G. (2010). *L'estime de soi, un passeport pour la vie*. Montréal, CHU St-Justine. Canada
- [17.] ESTIENNE, F. (1996). *Les bégaiements*. Paris : Masson
- [18.] FELOUZIS, G. (1993). Interactions en classe et réussite scolaire : une analyse des différences filles-garçons. *Revue française de sociologie*, 34 (2), 199-222.
- [19.] JINGER, Serge (2015). *Conférence sur cerveau droit, cerveau gauche, la différence entre les hommes et les femmes*. Consulté dans www.psychos-ressources.com, le 17 Avril 2022 à 9h 18.
- [20.] HARTER, S. (1998). *Comprendre l'estime de soi de l'enfant et de l'adolescent : considérations historiques, théoriques et méthodologiques*. In M. Bolognini, & Y. Prêteur, (Eds.), *Estime de soi, Perspectives développementales*. Lausanne : Delachaux et Niestlé.
- [21.] KONÉ, R. (1997). Statut social de la mère et performances de l'élève. *Revue Ivoirienne des Sciences de l'Education*, 1, 41-54.
- [22.] LAWRENCE, D. (1988). *Enhancing self-esteem in the classroom*. London : Paul Chapman Publishing.
- [23.] LE HUCHE, F. (2004). *Communication et interaction langagière dans le bégaiement*.
- [24.] MALANDAIN, C. (1997). Scolarité et développement de la personnalité. In: *Revue française de pédagogie*, volume 93, 1990. pp. 119-122.
- [25.] PARADIS, R. & Vitaro, F. (1992). Définition et mesure du concept de soi chez les enfants en difficulté d'adaptation sociale : une recension critique des écrits. *Revue canadienne de psychoéducation*, 21 (2), 93-114.
- [26.] HUMBERT, P, B. (1992). J'aimerais aimer l'école... Quelques données sur les images et les idéaux des élèves en difficulté scolaire. In B. Pierrehumbert (Ed.), *l'échec à l'école : échec de l'école ?* Neuchâtel: Delachaux et Niestlé.
- [27.] ROSENBERG, M. (1979). *Conceiving the self*. New York: Basic Books.
- [28.] ROSENWALD, F. (2008). La réussite scolaire des femmes et hommes en Europe. *Note d'information*, 11, 1-6.
- [29.] SEKA, Y., A., T. (2017). Du bégaiement au développement des compétences en mathématique : une étude transversale en terrain ivoirien de la commune de Bonoua. *Revue Ivoirienne des Sciences de l'Education*, N°17, ENS, Abidjan, pp24-36.
- [30.] VAN HOUT, A., et ESTIENNE, F., (1996). *Les bégaiements*. Paris : Masson.